

Australian Government

Department of Defence
Science and Technology

PREDICTING THE WETTED VIBRATION BEHAVIOR OF FLEXIBLE COMPOSITE HYDROFOILS

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In-air versus in-water

Typical aerofoil structure

Cavitation

Typical hydrofoil structure

Cavitation Erosion

Reduced Problem

To make design, manufacture, testing an analysis easier we use hydrofoils as a proxy for more complicated blade geometries

Hydrofoil design

Glass-Basket

Basket weave (0/90)

130 g/m²

Glass-(0/90)

Biaxial (0/90)

600 g/m²

Carbon-UD

Unidirectional

300 g/m²

Glass-Mat

Continuous filament skins / Polyolefin scaffold core

780 g/m²

Can change material, layup sequence and orientation to dramatically alter the hydrofoils

- Flexibility
- Twisting behaviour
- Vibration behaviour

Effect of material anisotropy on flow induced vibration

$Re=0.8e6, \alpha_0=16^\circ$

Distributed strain sensing

Optical Fibre Bragg Grating (FBG)

- Three arrays of nine FBGs
- Measures longitudinal strain
- 2 kHz acquisition rate
- Spectral resolution of 0.16 Hz

Vibration experiment setup

- Environment
 - Air
 - Water (distilled)
- Excitation
 - Burst random, sweep & chirp profiles
 - 10-1000 Hz
 - 100 averages
 - Varying excitation voltage
- Data acquisition
 - 2 kHz acquisition rate
 - Synchronisation achieved through NI Compact DAQ 9188 XT chassis
- Data analysis
 - Commercial software LMS Test Lab (PolyMax™)

Test setup (Wet)

Natural frequencies

In air

In water

Excitation profile: 100 average of 6 s burst random, 4 V amplitude

In water frequency coalescence & damping

Excitation profile: 100 average of 6 s burst random, 4 V amplitude

Observed frequency coalescence

Drop in damping due to frequency coalescence

FEA Structural Model

2 mm

microscopy
hydrofoil cross-section

Mechanical properties
coupon test

25491 Continuum Shell
(SCR8) Elements

Material	Ply thickness (mm)	Density (g/cm ³)	E ₁₁ (GPa)	E ₂₂ (GPa)	ν ₁₂	G ₁₂ (GPa)
Glass-Basket	0.15	1.66	15.3	12.8	0.13	3.0
Glass-(0/90)	0.58	1.75	15.1	19.3	0.03	4.2
Glass-Mat	2.40	1.37	6.8	5.0	0.30	2.5
Carbon-UD	0.26	1.59	117.8	13.4	0.25	3.9
Resin		1.20	3.27		0.3	

Static cantilever results

- Cantilever tests (experimental & FEA)
- 1 kN load @ mid span
- Measure leading and trailing edge tip displacements

carbon fibre angle

carbon fibre angle

Coupled Structural-Acoustic Simulations

- Fluid domain uses linear hexahedron (AC3D8) acoustic elements
- Mesh size 2367077 elements
- Non reflecting boundary conditions at fluid surfaces
- Fully coupled analysis
- No mesh adaptively (assume small displacement)

Mesh refinement near structure

Model Validation – In water response

GC00

GC45

Experimental

Structural-Acoustic Model

Influence of Carbon-UD Angle

Influence of Bending Stiffness

Summary

- **Frequency coalescence observed in the wetted condition**
 - Frequency coalescence related to a coupling between bending and torsional modes.
 - Frequency coalescence resulted in a reduction in damping ratio
- **Coupled structural-acoustic approach was able to predict reasonably well**
 - Natural frequencies
 - Mode shapes
 - A number of likely regions of mode coalescence
- **However, the structural-acoustic model did not predict one experimentally determined mode 3-4 coalescence for a hydrofoil at low span-wise bending stiffness**

Thanks for listening!

Acknowledgments

This project was supported by the Defence Science and Technology Group, the University of Tasmania and the US Office of Naval Research (Dr. Ki-Han Kim, Program Officer) and ONR Global (Dr. Woei-Min Lin) through NICOP S&T Grant N62909-11-1-7013. The authors would like to acknowledge the assistance of Mr Steven Kent and Mr Robert Wrigley from the Australian Maritime College for their essential help with setting up and carrying out the forced vibration experiments.